

Rediscovery of *Oxyina obesa* Loew (Diptera: Tephritidae) in Spain

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Oxyina obesa Loew, 1862, remained known hitherto only from a holotype ♀ from “Spain” (Loew, 1862; Hendel, 1927) was recently reared from *Artemisia campestris glutinosa* in Spain: León, San Juan de Paluezas (50°37'32.45" N 29°29'46.40" E) stems with galls, 1 ♀, coll. 26.02.2010, exit 16.03.2011 (Pérez Hidalgo leg.) (SIZK). The plant had reddish bud galls, which possibly were induced by *Oedaspis* sp., rather than *Oxyina*. *O. obesa* shares the wing pattern and shape of the aculeus with *O. albipila* Loew, 1869, whose larvae develop in the young shoots of *Artemisia* spp., unducing no galls, as well as *O. parietina* (Linnaeus) and *O. stackelbergi* Korneyev (Korneyev, 1990). This species differs from other *Oxyina* species by white anterior and posterior orbital setae and black posterior notopleural setae. See Korneyev & Evstigneev (2013) for illustrations of the holotype and further diagnostic characters.

Figs 1–9. *Oxyina obesa* Loew, ♀ from Leon: 1 — total view, lateral, 2 — head, lateral, 3 — head and thorax, dorsal, 4 — abdomen, dorsal, 5 — wing, 6 — eversible membrane, ventral, 7 — aculeus, ventral, 8 — aculeus apex, enlarged, 9 — spermatheca.

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Received 18.06.2013 Accepted 24.06.2013 Published 25.06.2013

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